

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING CAPITAL STRUCTURE IN COMPANIES IN MODERN TIMES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495155>

Abstract

All successful businesses need a sound financial management system that ensures efficient use of financial resources and effective management of day-to-day financial transactions. The concept and practice of strategic financial management includes all major financial decisions and practices to be made by owners or managers in the management structure of an enterprise. Past research shows that economic planning, financial record keeping, external professional advice and financial security have a positive relationship with success in businesses. Although the importance of effective and efficient financial management on growth and profitability, which are the main goals of enterprises, is generally recognized, there is a limited number of studies in the financial management literature on strategic financial management applications in enterprises. The number of studies on the growth and competitiveness of these practices in enterprises is equally small.

Keywords: capital structure, economic planning, financial opportunities, financial management, financial management.

Enterprises in our country have achieved significant development and progress in recent years, especially with the positive effect of the state-funded support policy. However, as in many developing countries, enterprises face significant challenges in general management, research and development, skilled human resources, financing and marketing. Among these challenges, financial management is at the top of the list, one of the areas with the greatest need for technical knowledge. Due to the problems of financial management of enterprises in our country, the difficulty of accessing financial resources and insufficient financial resources, a large part of the academic work in this field has been limited until now, and a large part of the conducted academic work has been directed to the problems related to limited financial resources. As a result, research on other aspects of financial management (cash management, capital management, investment activity, debt and receivables management, shareholder management, cost management, etc.) that are of great importance to enterprises has remained limited. Enterprises in our country are unable to attract professional managers and receive consulting services from abroad due to the high cost, mainly financial management. In addition, entrepreneurs may not want to see their own knowledge and experience in the decision-making process and do not want to transfer the decision-making mechanisms in the enterprise to another person. All these reasons can lead to the failure of a healthy and efficient financial management system. The economic environment in which enterprises operate is highly

complex, high risks and competition, financial management make these problems even more important, and the consequences that enterprises can often experience.

Researches conducted in the financial fields of enterprises are focused on the financial opportunities and problems faced by enterprises in this field both in the world and in our country. Research shows that enterprises operating in developing countries face greater external resource challenges than those in developed countries. This situation is reflected in academic research, and it appears that less research has been done on the financial management practices of enterprises than on financing problems.

It is clear that the increase in foreign financing opportunities and improvement of conditions for enterprises are taken into account, especially in the case of insufficient capital accumulation in our country. But in order to achieve financial resources in enterprises, the efficient use of these resources is equally important. For example, many businesses that can increase sales as a result of successful production and marketing activities face the risk of being unable to pay their debts due to difficulties in collecting their receivables and going into bankruptcy. Likewise, companies that finance their long-term investments with short-term financing or misrepresent their cost analysis may struggle to achieve growth and profitability goals. Lack of cash management and inventory control in a number of businesses with sufficient capital can lead to business failure. Despite these results, it was found that the owners or managers of enterprises in our country do not pay

enough attention to strategic financial management practices, which are of great importance in achieving sustainable development and increasing their competitiveness.

In the studies, the most important reasons for the failure of enterprises were financial planning, unplanned growth, low strategic and financial forecast, excessive fixed investment and wrong capital management.

Strategic financial management is defined as financial management theories related to the most accurate way of financing enterprises, the most effective evaluation and management of investment, and the decision to release or distribute profits in the most appropriate manner. Financial strategies should have objectives, methods and alternatives intended to improve and optimize financial management in order to achieve the objectives of enterprises. As it is clear from these definitions, strategic financial management should first of all define the goals of the enterprise and then plan and organize financial management tools and processes to achieve these goals. In the processes of strategic financial management, after the financial planning stage, the implementation of these plans intended for the main goals of the enterprise is carried out in the most efficient and effective way, without losing any time for possible violations in the process, the activity of the evaluation period is the basis of strategic financial management.

Although theories in the field of financial management have long attracted the attention of academics, in recent years financial management practices have become the subject of academic research. McMahon, Hutchinson and Forsaith (McMahon, 1993), the work of corporate financial management practices in Australia, the United Kingdom and the United States, is among the leading studies. Since this study, many researchers have discussed various financial management practices in enterprises.

In the work done in connection with enterprises in our country, in the problems related to financial management in enterprises, it shows that effective and ineffective financial management applications have an important place in these problems. In addition to limited access to capital and credit, enterprises in our country have significant problem areas in financial management and gaps in cash management. Poor cash flow planning over time does not allow business owners to avoid shortfalls in business financing with equity or personal funds. If this situation continues for a long time, it leads to the dissolution of the enterprise and the enterprise remains in a difficult situation. In addition to cash management, many strategic financial management practices, such as receivables and inventory (supply) management, debt maturity adjustment, investment budget, play an important role in the growth and operation of enterprises in our country.

The financial resources of enterprises reflect the totality of incomes and cash in general at the disposal of any economic entity. In special enterprises, financial resources, which include the processes of formation, distribution and use of income, generally have obligations to the formation of special purpose money funds

at the enterprise level, as well as to other structures. These obligations are formed on the basis of payments to the state budget of various structural bodies. Financial reserves are formed through special funds. But in general, we can note that profit is the financial resources of the enterprise and the main source of formation. And the profit reflects the monetary expression of the first collections created as a result of the activities of the enterprises, and at this time it is reflected as the result of the financial activity of the enterprises as an economic category. Increasing profit by enterprises, which includes various features of the financial economic activity of enterprises, also leads to an increase in financial reserves, and this, in turn, leads to the health and strengthening of the financial system. At the same time, the results of the production and economic activity of the enterprises were expressed in the form of money, and the income to be obtained from the financial economic activity was also reflected in their future activity. In the conditions of the market economy, the income obtained from the products they produce is considered as the method of formation of enterprise finance. A part of this income is spent on production, and the other part is spent on expenses related to the organization of this production in general. The remaining part is distributed to pay wages or the enterprise's obligations to other structures, and the remaining amount reflects the financial reserves obtained by the enterprise through collectors. Financial reserves formed at the expense of 2 sources will ensure the complete circulation of capital, which plays an important role in determining the financial situation in general.

When talking about the mechanism for improving financing methods, we should first of all note that when using financing methods in the financial management of entrepreneurial activity in each country. The issue of using different methods varies depending on the state policy. In this direction, in our country, it is necessary to expand the investment activity and the use of funds attracted from outside in the direction of improving the activities related to the state financing, as well as the self-financing method in enterprises. In the case of self-financing, enterprises carry out financing at the expense of their own income. In the case of self-financing, enterprises constantly try to increase their reserves and obtain maximum profits with minimum costs. When using various methods of financing, both by the state and by enterprises, various measures should be taken in order to eliminate existing deficiencies and solve existing problems, as well as to improve the activity.

Production, workforce, sales of finished products, etc. participate in all these processes at the enterprise. From the distribution and redistribution of financial results, the process of additional financing and the overall interconnected system of indicators ultimately characterize the financial situation of the enterprise. The profit represented as a result of the enterprise's economic activity in general, reflecting the value of the realized part of its net income, stimulates enterprises to obtain more profit. In general, every enterprise tries to get maximum profit by using resources sparingly and to regulate their activities through this.

Let's take a look at the general principles of organizing financial resources in enterprises. These include the following

- The first principle is that financial reserves are formed in enterprises, but as we mentioned, they are formed through attracted funds and special funds. Special financial reserves are formed from the moment of establishment of enterprises and are determined when the charter fund is established. The main reason for this is that in order to realize any economic activity, the enterprise itself must first have its own financial security.

- The second principle is the preparation of a financial plan by forecasting the past and present period of the enterprise's financial and economic activity and future. Drawing up a financial plan acts as the basis for the normal and healthy functioning of enterprises, and many issues are reflected here, such as financial reserves, capital, income and expenditure forecasting for the purpose of ensuring financial activity.

- This last principle uses the preservation of working capital. The essence of this principle is that if the amount of special working capital decreases, then there is a danger that the enterprise will operate more normally in the future and lose financial stability. Therefore, in order to preserve working capital, it is important in the regulation of financial economic activity.

Financial sources necessary for financing enterprise activities are divided into 3 parts: short, medium and long term. If we consider the content of each one separately, when talking about the previous short-term financial sources, we should say that these financial sources are the most used and repayable funds. Short-term sources of finance are returned after being used within a year, or they no longer have any value after this period. Short-term sources of finance are more focused on the purchase of current assets, which generally studies the methods of attracting and managing funds. These funding sources include:

1. Factoring
2. Short-term bank loans
3. Proceeds from the sale of loans
4. Short-term securities sold in the stock market
5. Other short-term sources

In general, financial management in the operation of these enterprises is usually performed through the selection of the source of finance and the execution of financing accordingly. In modern times, there is a need for their financing in order to ensure the normal functioning of enterprises. Therefore, they are always classified in the form of financing and investments, regardless of their use and acquisition.

Current financing is a type of financing intended for the purpose of carrying out the current activities of the enterprise, and it is more typical for simple reproduction. Investment, regardless of its type, does not act as a source of financing, but simply as one of the financing stages of enterprises.

Taking into account that financing by these enterprises is carried out through these 2 main sources, the fact that enterprises act as a source of financing through their own funds includes the funds they have attracted since the period of their first creation. Thus, businesses usually raise a certain amount of funds by issuing additional shares and attracting new shareholders. However, despite this, in modern times, enterprises operate simply through the funds raised and cannot obtain normal profits. Therefore, it is necessary for them to use their own funds for normal operation. At the same time, if the enterprise carries out financing at the expense of its own funds, then its obligation to any 2nd parties is not formed. In this case, the obtained profit is used for refinancing as agreed between the members of the management board of the enterprise.

Businesses also raise funds by issuing additional shares for financing. In various literatures, the issue of additional shares and the raising of cash funds have been evaluated in different ways. It is considered beneficial for the firm to use the sources of financing of the enterprise through the issue of shares, to obtain short-term funds. One of the main reasons for this is that when issuing additional shares, that cash is actually the company's own funds. In general, we can note that financing at the expense of one's own funds is considered effective not only at the level of the enterprise, but also from a macro-economic and social point of view. The main reason for this is that during the period of economic stagnation, in a situation where sales are reduced, or because the obligations of self-financed enterprises are less, there is no danger of their activity going out of business or going bankrupt. The importance of the efficient operation of enterprises from the macroeconomic point of view is that in countries that have chosen the path of market economy, enterprises fulfill the economic stability policy of the state by meeting the population's demand for consumer goods and reducing unemployment.

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